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Participatory epidemiology and community-led zoonotic disease risk reduction in Cambodia

Chanthy, Srey¹, Theara, Teng¹, Ratana, Chhan¹, Sarin, Neang¹, Malen, Ken,¹ Dou, Sok¹, Gheri, Bruno² Lantagne, Daniele³, Bunna, Chea⁴, Mariner, Jeffrey^{3,5}, Veasna, Duong⁶, Thavry, Hoem⁶, Gold, Elizabeth⁷, Faustman, Elaine⁸, Peterson, Jennifer⁹, Gass, Jonathon^{3,10}, Nutter, Felicia³, Burgess, Tristan⁵ & the STOP Spillover Consortium³

1. TetraTech ARD, Phnom Penh, Cambodia
2. Cummings School of Veterinary Medicine, Tufts University, North Grafton, MA, USA
3. Friedman School of Nutrition, Tufts University, Boston, MA, USA
4. Royal University of Agriculture, Phnom Penh, Cambodia
5. Center for Wildlife Studies, South Freeport, ME, USA
6. Institut Pasteur du Cambodge, Phnom Penh, Cambodia
7. JSI Boston, MA, USA
8. Institute for Risk Analysis and Risk Communication, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA
9. TetraTech ARD, Burlington VT, USA
10. School of Medicine, Tufts University, Boston, MA, USA

* tburgess@centerforwildlifestudies.org

This story comes from the country team implementing USAID STOP Spillover in Cambodia and the consortium who support their work. The Cambodia team has diverse personal and professional backgrounds, both rural and urban, and is composed of both young people who have known only the modern Cambodia, as well as representation from the generation of elders who have lived through the upheavals and changes in Cambodia in the late 20th century. The global consortium supporting the Cambodia team includes mainly advisors in social and behaviour change, practitioners of participatory epidemiology and scientists trained in western knowledge systems.

The international development sector in general, and One Health/Global Health development work in particular, though founded in good intentions, have included many threads of neocolonialism, paternalism and have tended to elevate the perspectives of western scientists over the lived experience of the communities who are apparently being aided. This creates not only ethical problems, but practical ones too. Interventions that do not make sense in a local context are unlikely to be sustained, or if enforced by government policy, may harm the intended beneficiaries. As such, hearing the voices of the host community and building real meaningful participation – working in true partnership with the community - should be prioritised in any work seeking to support sustainable development.

Designing ways to ensure that the voices of communities where we work are heard has been central to the work of STOP Spillover in Cambodia from its inception. This work is not trivial, and it is a pathway of learning both for practitioners and especially for funders, who must have the patience to wait for the process of building trust and collaboration to bear fruit, and also the courage and flexibility to adapt when participants use their influence to make changes to project plans and activities.

Through a series of images, sound recordings and stories from the field, we bring you the narrative of working to understand knowledge, attitudes, practices and zoonotic disease risk perceptions in a community engaged in bat guano farming, and the journey of designing risk reduction interventions with this community as well as developing a One Health disease surveillance system with district, provincial and national government & non-government partners – a system founded in participatory epidemiology at the interface level.